

Managing Editor's Column

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This regular issue presents 10 papers co-authored by 23 authors from 8 countries on 3 continents. But not only the geographic variety, but also the great spread of topics witnesses to the “universality” of J.UCS. I trust that each of you will find at least one interesting paper from your area of research!

The first 7 papers have been peer-reviewed by the members of our editorial board. Let me use this opportunity to thank the editors for their efforts, support and enthusiasm which is essential for the continuing existence and success of our journal.

The last three articles are extended versions of papers originally presented at the Innovations Conference for Knowledge Management, New Media Technology and Semantic Systems (TRIPLE-I '08) in Graz, Austria. The papers were selected by one of the Editors-in-Chief, Klaus Tochtermann and Gisela Granitzer. Gisela Granitzer comments on the selection:

“The three papers address aspects of Web 2.0 in various contexts. The first paper discusses common patterns of learning and collaborating in 3D Virtual Worlds and categorise these alongside design effort and added value. A multi source tag recommender system which allows the users to select to which degree criteria such as content or existing tags should be integrated in the tag recommendation process is introduced in the second paper. In the third paper the authors assess the adoption of Web 2.0 features by traditional Danish news media and claim that new models for business model development are needed. ”

Finally, it's a pleasure to inform you that all issues and articles published in 2008 have now also been assigned a digital object identifier which you can find above the abstracts.

Enjoy the issue – the next ones are already in preparation!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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